

Bhūtasamkhyā list

A complete record of the bhūtasamkhyās (object words) used in the text portions covered in this study.

In each case, the list entry begins with the standard number word for that number, for example eka is the standard number word, 'one'.

1 eka

2 dvi

pakṣa: PI 8.191, 8.213

yugma: BK vy 57; PI 8.191, 8.193

3 tri

agni: BK vy 116, 128

guṇa: PI 8.121, 8.122, 8.225, 8.256

rāma: PI 8.183

4 catur

turya: BK vy 127; MC 4.33; PI 8.25, 8.106, 8.133, 8.145 (twice), 8.166 (twice),
8.184, 8.190, 8.194, 8.196 (twice), 8.205 (twice), 8.210, 8.211, 8.223, 9.21
(twice), 9.43

veda: MY 4.y+7; PI 8.182, 8.191

5 pañca

pr̥thivyādika: PI 8.188

bhūta: BK vy 114; PI 8.186, 8.187, 8.199, 8.236, 8.249, 8.257 (twice), 9.41-42

śara: PI 8.187

6 ṣaṣ

ṛtu: PI 8.187, PI 9.11

rasa: BK vy 116; MC 4.21; PI 8.188, PI 8.226

7 sapta

muni: PI 8.184

svara: PI 8.226

Bhūtasamkhyā list

8 aṣṭa

diś: MC 3.30

vasu: MC 4.33; PI 6.66, 8.26

9 nava

tāra: PI 8.196

randhra: BK vy 31, 118; MC 4.21

10 daśa

pañkti: PI 8.227

11 ekādaśa

rudra: PI 8.143, 9.27, 9.91